

LEASING PROFESSIONAL ATHLETES: PROBLEMS OF CIVIL LAW REGULATION

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Abstract: the article analyzes the problems of legal regulation of the lease of professional athletes based on the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Attention is paid to legal acts regulating these relations, as well as the conditions on which the parties agree when leasing a professional athlete. It is noted that the athlete lease agreement, as well as the transfer agreement, has a complex legal nature. They interact with the norms of both civil and labor law.

Keywords: sport, sports relations, sports contract, athlete lease, national legislation.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of physical culture and sports is of paramount importance. In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, to the Oliy Majlis (Parliament) of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 20, 2022, it was said about the need for “mass involvement of people of different ages in physical culture” and “ensuring a healthy lifestyle of a person”. [1] In the New Edition of the Constitution of Uzbekistan, Article 48 states that “The State creates conditions for the development of physical culture and sports, the formation of a healthy lifestyle among the population”. [2] The progress of physical culture and sports relations in our country is very dynamic, which, in turn, requires constant attention to improving the regulatory framework, the creation of fundamentally new legislative acts that consolidate the achievements of physical culture and sports in our country.

Therefore, the study and improvement of sports law norms is of great importance.

One of the topics that, in our opinion, should be given more attention in the field of sports law is the legal aspects of contractual relations in sports. The activities of an athlete in our country, as well as activities in other areas, must comply with the principles established by regulatory acts.

Today, in our opinion, very important are the issues of legal regulation of the transitions (transfer) of athletes from one sports organization to another under a valid contract. as well as its lease.

The right of an athlete to transfer to another physical education and sports organization is, in our opinion, one of the main ones that should be provided to the athlete in his contract.

The laws of many countries have established norms regulating such relations. For example, in the acts regulating relations regarding the transfer and lease of athletes of such

countries as Germany, France, Great Britain, Brazil, Argentina and many others, the regulation of relations arising between an athlete and a sports organization regarding the transfer of an athlete to another sports organization or his lease is directly indicated. Thus, the Brazilian Law No. 6354 of September 2, 1976 regulated "the issues of the transfer of a professional athlete to another club." [3]

In some of the author's works, attention was also paid to this issue [4,5]

Until recently, national legislation did not establish rules for the transfer of athletes from one sports organization to another. Moreover, the concepts of "athlete transfer" and "athlete lease" do not exist in our legislation.

The new Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which entered into force in April 2023, defines only the temporary transfer of an athlete from one employer to another and says nothing about lease, transition or "transfer". These rules are established in clubs for various sports. For example, the Regulations of the Football Association of Uzbekistan adopted the procedure for the transfer of players from club to club, approved by the Executive Committee of the Football Association of Uzbekistan on 11.02.2021. [6]

Legal regulation of temporary transfers of professional athletes is mainly contained in legal acts of sports federations and associations. Another part of the provisions affecting this institution is contained in labor and civil legislation) - for example, Article 503 of the New Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Features of legal regulation of athletes' labor", [7] however, at the moment, neither the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, [8] nor the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Culture and Sports" [9] contain rules regulating the application of a transfer agreement on the terms of "lease".

Under a transfer agreement on the terms of "lease", one professional sports club (the lessor) undertakes to transfer on the terms of "lease" to another professional sports club (the lessee) for a certain period of time a professional athlete, who in turn undertakes to transfer from one professional sports club to another. The agreement is consensual, fixed-term and compensated. The bilaterally binding nature of the agreement is evidenced by the fact that the lessor club must transfer the athlete to the lessee club, and the latter has an obligation to accept the athlete and pay the lessor club a transfer fee and other payments agreed upon by the parties (including compensation for the training, preparation and improvement of the athlete's skills).

Most of the obligations under the contract have a clearly expressed non-property nature, since the relationship on the transfer of a football player from one club to another and back does not pursue the transfer of any material benefits. This means that the property value of the contract is only the transfer amount paid by the tenant club, as well as the amount of compensation for the training, preparation and improvement of the athlete's skills, which indicates the compensability of the transfer agreement on the terms of "lease" [8]. The presence of a term in this contract distinguishes it from a transfer agreement, under which the athlete moves to another club on a permanent basis. In essence, unlike a transfer agreement, under a transfer agreement on the terms of "lease",

the athlete moves to another sports club twice, accordingly, in accordance with Art. 93 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, he is transferred to another job twice [7]. This means that an entry about dismissal and hiring to another job is made in the football player's work book twice. However, the Regulations, for example, of the Football Association of Uzbekistan (FAU), do not recognize the return of an athlete to the leasing club as a second transfer. Also, this agreement is tripartite, the athlete acts as a participant (party) to the agreement. The legal nature of this agreement is very ambiguous, some scientists find many contradictions contained in agreements of this kind. In turn, most researchers classify it as a civil law agreement [10,11]. The standard form of a transfer agreement on lease terms is approved by sports federations, for example, in the appendix to the Regulations of the Football Association of Uzbekistan (FAU) and is mandatory for use by the relevant professional football clubs.

Since the transition (transfer) of the athlete under the specified agreement is temporary, there is a possibility of its confusion with a temporary transfer to another job in labor legislation. However, based on the literal interpretation of Art. 92 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it follows that a temporary transfer is possible only with one employer, and under a transfer agreement on the terms of "lease" the athlete's employer changes [7]. Thus, it is not possible to recognize the relationship on the temporary transition (transfer) of a football player as labor. Whether any agreement belongs to civil law is also determined by its subject. There is no consensus on the definition of the subject of a transfer contract on the terms of "lease" in the science of sports and civil law. Some scientists believe that it is a temporary transfer of an athlete from one club to another for a certain period. A temporary transfer on a "lease" basis in accordance with Article 1 of the AFU Regulations is recognized as a transfer of a professional athlete from a professional sports club for which he is registered, to temporarily compete for another professional sports club - this is the period between the first and second registration periods or the period between the second registration period and the end of the current sports season [6].

The duration of the transition must be established by the parties and cannot be shorter than the terms stipulated by the said regulations. Others recognize the following as the subject: 1) actions aimed at the assignment of a claim, the object is the property right to compensation, the object is the property right to the services of an athlete; 2) services for the transfer of a player to another sports club, and the object in turn is recognized as services [12, 13]; 3) services for the training and preparation of an athlete, the object also refers to services; [14, 15] 4) assignment of the property right to services for an athlete's access to competitions - transfer rights (rights to register a professional (non-amateur) athlete in the relevant sports association, the object is the property right to services for an athlete's access to competitions [16].

Based on the literal interpretation in accordance with Art. 535 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the definition of a transfer agreement on the terms of

"lease", the object moved from one entity to another is the temporary transfer of an athlete from one club to another [8]. The object of this agreement is transfer rights, which should be understood as the rights to register an athlete in the relevant sports club, the rights of an athlete to perform for the colors of the relevant club, etc. In accordance with this, one party, the lessor club, transfers transfer rights (the rights to register a professional athlete in the relevant sports association) to the other party, the lessee club, for a certain period, and the other party, the lessee club, pays the lessor club (the owner of the transfer) compensation for the preparation and improvement of the skills of a professional athlete. The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not provide for such an object of civil rights, therefore, we believe that a temporary transfer should be understood as the assignment of the right to claim transfer rights for a certain period. Transfer rights belonging to the lessor club on the basis of an employment contract with an athlete may be transferred by it to the lessee club under a transaction in accordance with Article 313 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan [8]. Thus, by its nature, a transfer agreement on the terms of "lease" is an assignment of the right of claim for a certain period. Under it, the lessee club receives the transfer rights of a temporary transfer of a specific athlete. In order to consider this agreement concluded, it is necessary to designate the content of the transfer of a specific professional athlete in it. Thus, despite the differences in the views of various researchers on the issue of the presence of a civil law nature in a transfer agreement on the terms of "lease", it is not possible to speak of its absence.

Continuing to analyze the national legislation, we note that Article 535 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides

The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not contain the concept of "lease of an athlete". The Civil Code only provides the concept of "types of objects of civil rights", where the object is "things, results of intellectual activity, as well as personal non-property rights and other tangible and intangible benefits" (article), i.e. individuals cannot be the object of a lease agreement, like any other. However, the lease of an athlete implies that the object of such an agreement is an individual. Taking into account the above, based on world practice, in order to improve national legislation, it seems correct to make additions to Article 81 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, where it is indicated that the object of the agreement may be an individual without prejudice to dignity", and in Article 535 it is indicated that in exceptional cases directly specified in Article 81, the object of the lease agreement may be an individual. [8]

When an athlete is temporarily transferred to another employer to continue practicing professional sports, the employment contract concluded with the previous employer is suspended and renewed upon expiration of the athlete's temporary transfer. This is an innovation for the labor law of Uzbekistan, and, as a result, some issues, such as the question of where the employee's work record book is stored, have not yet been resolved.

Based on Article 81 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, only

information about the transfer to another permanent job is entered into the work record book. Information about a temporary transfer is not subject to entry [7]. It is considered possible, by analogy with the law, to apply the procedure for filling out the work record book for a person appointed as a temporary (anti-crisis) manager.

Legislative experience of foreign countries shows that the work record book of an athlete or coach may remain with the original employer for the entire period of transfer. The employer may also make entries in the work record book of an athlete or coach on the suspension of a fixed-term employment contract for the period of temporary transfer to another employer, on the renewal of a fixed-term employment contract [17]. At the same time, representatives of, for example, Russian science came to the opinion that when an athlete is temporarily transferred to another employer, the work record book should be transferred to the employer at the place of temporary work, since for the period of temporary transfer the athlete is bound by labor relations only with one employer, who should keep the work record book. We support this opinion, since in practice there are many examples of a temporary transfer of an athlete to another club on loan and, naturally, he develops labor relations with this new employer [18, 19].

In addition, the provisions of Article 503 of the new Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan also note that "During the period of temporary transfer (sports lease), the athlete and the employer at the place of temporary work are fully subject to the rules established by labor legislation and other acts containing labor law standards, with the features established by this article" [7].

So, the athlete lease agreement, as well as the transfer agreement, has a complex nature. As we have seen, the norms of civil and labor law interact in them. Also, these agreements are poorly regulated by regulatory legal acts. Therefore, we recommend carefully spelling out all the rights and obligations of the parties, responsibility for their failure to fulfill them.

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